

Data management plan

Project title: **Enhancing Research and Innovation Synergies for Schools of Economics and Business**

Project no. 101159106 — RIS4SEB

D1.2 Data management plan (due in M6), to be update in M15 and M36

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Executive summary

This document outlines the data management practices adopted for the RIS4SEB project, emphasizing our commitment to ensuring data is managed effectively, securely, and ethically. Key elements include:

1. **Adherence to FAIR Principles:** The project strictly follows the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data management principles, ensuring that data is managed efficiently and remains usable for future research endeavors.
2. **Philosophy of Openness:** We uphold the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary,” balancing the need for transparency with obligations to protect sensitive and personal data.
3. **Trusted Repository Usage:** All open-access data and documents are deposited in [Zenodo](#), a trusted and widely recognized repository, ensuring long-term preservation and accessibility. We follow the DataCite’s Metadata Schema for data descriptions.
4. **Dedicated Personnel:** Each beneficiary institution has appointed a responsible person to oversee data management in line with project requirements. These are:
 - **Aneta Kašílková** at VŠE,
 - **Asta Savanevičienė** at KTU,
 - **Karmo Kroos** at EBS, and
 - **Niccolò Cusumano** at UB.
5. **Secure Internal Platform:** Data is securely stored in a private and protected shared MS Teams group, leveraging the Office 365 infrastructure to provide compliance, privacy, and security.
6. **GDPR Compliance:** The collection and management of personal data strictly follow GDPR regulations.

This approach ensures a robust framework for managing the diverse data generated throughout the RIS4SEB project.

Introduction

The overall objective of RIS4SEB is to design and pilot three strategies aiming at enabling and facilitating effective synergies between Horizon Europe and other national/regional funds, by strengthening Internationalization of R&I widening actors, developing Human Resources, and improving Research management capacity and overall competitiveness of the widening partners.

RIS4SEB is a Coordination and support Action project, so it is not expected to generate a large amount of specialized research data. However, various types of data will be reused and generated throughout the project's duration. Ensuring the protection and exploitation of this data and the results across different Work Packages (WPs) is a key focus. The Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to outline the principles and guidelines for data management that consortium partners will follow regarding all data collected and generated for RIS4SEB.

As the DMP is a living document and this is the first version, much of the reused or generated data can be presently unclear. In subsequent versions, we count with specifications of information about the actual data management processes in each WP and the whole consortium.

The DMP follows the Horizon Europe template for Data Management Plans. Section 1 outlines the types of data defined within the project and provides a summary of data collected and reused per WP. Section 2 explains how RIS4SEB will uphold the four 'FAIR Data' principles: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Section 3 covers other project outputs. Section 4 details the allocation of resources. Section 5 addresses data security. Finally, Section 6 discusses any ethical issues related to data collection and sharing.

The document attached to this DMP includes recommendations for data organization and access to the data generated in the project. These recommendations will help clarify basic data handling practices during the project to meet the FAIR principles and ensure the secure storage of sensitive data generated during the project.

1 Data Summary

Participants in the WPs and participants in planned surveys are almost exclusively staff of partner universities. In the project, they will provide data regarding their professional areas of expertise or compile or derive data from pre-existing relevant data from their home universities. More detailed information about collected and reused data is evident from the tables.

1.1 Non-equipment datasets

We don't need any special equipment for collection of the data. We collect data from questionnaires, and we analyse existing documents.

The non-equipment datasets are:

- VŠE in blue,
- KTU in green,
- EBS in orange,
- UB in pink.

Work Package	Output (Deliverable)	Dataset description & Data collection method	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data Format
WP2	D2.1 – Joint internationalization strategy for R&I	Qualitative text data: Research group description (survey) Strategy high level information (survey)	Specific objective (SO) SO1 to create and pilot a joint internationalization strategy for R&I	Pdf Doc xls
	D2.2 – Report on networks analysis	Qualitative text data: Research labs description (survey)	SO2 to facilitate access to networks and communities	Pdf Doc
	D2.3 – Analysis of research calls suitable for the available ERDF (or equivalent) funded infrastructure	Qualitative text data: Research labs description (survey)	SO3 to pave the way to overcoming the locked in effect for former mono-beneficiaries funded under ERDF and a better use of R&I infrastructure funded under ERDF	Pdf Doc
WP3	D3.1 – Human Resources Strategy	Qualitative text data: checklist for HR strategy development, University descriptions, Research topics, SWOT-TOWS analysis Quantitative data: past HE projects,	SO4 To develop a Human resources strategy	Doc / PDF Online open-ended questionnaires – TXT / PDF Focus group reports (EBS, VŠE, KTU SEB)

		The mutual HR strategy will be tested using by external AB members (online questionnaire), The adaptation of strategy in every university will be evaluated in internal focus groups (FG discussion)		
	D3.2 – Report on job shadowing and training of research managers	Feedback online questionnaire	SO4 To develop a Human resources strategy	Online deed-back questionnaires – TXT / PDF (participants)
WP4	D4.1 – Report on Research management strategy implementation	Intra-university questionnaires (researchers, administrative support staff, research management staff, executive level; university bodies: deans’ and rectors’ collegiums, (inter)national advisory boards, academic senates)	SO6 To enhance institutional environment and processes through RM strategy	Online questionnaires – TXT / PDF
	D4.2 – Policy recommendations for synergies among research funding programmes	Not known yet	SO7 to produce policy recommendations for future synergies between research funding programmes	Not known yet
	D4.3 – Report on submitted project proposals	Text data	SO8 to pilot active ability to compete on an international level.	Doc/PDF

1.2 Re-used datasets

We have found the following non-reference datasets that we have considered for re-use:

Work Package	Output (Deliverable)	BEN	Dataset description	Does the institution / responsible partner have access to the data?	Conversion of the data format needed?
WP2	D2.1 – Joint internationalization strategy for R&I	VSE	Various quantitative secondary data – outputs of internal questionnaires Results of questionnaires “SURVEY AMONG ACADEMIC WORKERS: SCIENCE AND RESEARCH ON VSE” (May 2024)	It is available on internal storages of VSE. Owner of this dataset is Prague University of	Xls PDF

			<p>“Results of Ph.D. survey VŠE 2023”</p> <p>“Detailed analysis for KA3: transparent and effective set up of strategic HR management”</p> <p>“Employee survey OP JAK 9/2024”</p>	<p>Economics and Business.</p> <p>We already have a copy of these datasets.</p>	
		KTU	<p>Various quantitative secondary data – outputs of internal questionnaires and databases available at KTU.</p>	<p>It is available on internal storages of KTU. Owner of this dataset is KTU.</p>	<p>Xls PDF</p>
		UB	<p>List of relevant ERDF and Horizon funded projects (xls); Horizon Europe strategic plan 2025-2027 (pdf); Policy briefs and papers from European Commission; success stories and public reports from previous/on-going projects under the Widening participation and spreading excellence across Europe</p> <p>Standards for international accreditation (AACSB, EQUIS, AMBA)</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>No, xls, pdf</p>
	D2.2 – Report on networks analysis	EBS	<p>Quantitative data from publication databases (WoS/Scopus)</p> <p>Network analysis</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Excel (XML) file (other formats like TXT, CSV may also be available upon request)</p>
	D2.3 – Analysis of research calls suitable for the available ERDF (or equivalent) funded infrastructure	EBS	<p>Qualitative data - content analysis of upcoming calls</p>	<p>Not yet, but they will be</p>	<p>Doc (other formats like TXT, CSV, PDF may also be available upon request)</p>
WP3	D3.1 – Human Resources Strategy		<p>not known yet</p>	<p>not known yet</p>	<p>not known yet</p>
	D3.2 – Report on job shadowing and training of research managers		<p>none</p>	<p>none</p>	<p>none</p>

WP4	D4.1 – Report on Research management strategy implementation	ALL	Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025, Horizon funded projects linking to R&I in economics through Cordis database; database of potentially relevant EU associations and clusters	Yes	No
	D4.2 – Policy recommendations for synergies among research funding programmes		none	none	none
	D4.3 – Report on submitted project proposals		none	none	none

There is no need to harmonize different sources of existing data in our case.

1.3 Data formats and types

We will be using datasets in a suitable format for long-term archiving.

During the active research phase, we will use also proprietary file formats such as DOC or PDF. Nevertheless, for long-term archiving we will be using datasets in a suitable format such as Office Open XML, TXT, CSV or PDF/A.

For this project, only a small amount of data is expected to be created, so we do not expect problems with their storage.

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

FAIR is a central part of our data management; it is considered at every decision in our data management plan. We use the FAIR data process ourselves to make our use of the data as efficient as possible.

There is a consortium document with recommendations for file naming ([Annex 1](#)). We will be keeping the relationships between data clear in the file names. All the metadata in the file names also will be available in the proper metadata.

We provide metadata for all data. We follow the DataCite's Metadata Schema, which is compliant with the repository Zenodo. We will describe our data with rich and subject specific keywords.

All the datasets will be identified by the persistent identifier DOI, which is issued to every record in the repository Zenodo and it is part of the metadata description.

Metadata of all records in Zenodo are indexed in DataCite servers.

2.2 Making data accessible

We are working with the philosophy "*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*" for our data.

We will deposit the data, documents and results achieved in our project in the trusted repository Zenodo. We already have an [established profile](#) within the repository. Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.

The (meta)data deposited in Zenodo are accessible through free and standardised protocols (OAI-PMH and REST API) for information retrieval on the web. All metadata in Zenodo may be freely used under the CC0 waiver.

Nevertheless, some of the **data cannot become completely open because of legal and privacy reasons.**

Specifically, **full answers to the qualitative/quantitative research among university employees, especially when involving high management of the institutions, cannot become completely open.** Even through the processes of pseudonymization and anonymization, we are not able to achieve protection of personal data of the people involved, because they are a very small group of persons assigned to one specific institution and department and thus uniquely identifiable. For these reasons we are unable to ensure data protection according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The questionnaires and the analysis of the results of the questionnaires / synthesized reports will be openly available.

Additionally, part of the project outputs may not be completely open for commercial/business reasons. Each partner needs to protect the brand of its parent institution, and for these reasons it is possible that some information sensitive to the promotion of the institution's brand will be assessed as inappropriate for sharing. For each closed dataset/document will be appointed contact person who will evaluate/approve individual access requests. This person also will keep documentation concerning granted access.

Concerning the legal reasons, a data-sharing agreement will be required.

Metadata will be openly available. Metadata will be available in a form that can be harvested and indexed (managed by the repository Zenodo). The instructions on how to get access to the data will be described in a readme file that will be connected to the record.

We have a consortium agreement that arranges Intellectual Property.

Access to the data during the project is described in section 5. Data Security.

2.3 Making data interoperable

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- Office Open XML, TXT, CSV, PDF/A

They are standardized formats.

The records in Zenodo follow the DataCite's Metadata Schema and uses external vocabularies for licenses, funders and grants.

We won't use any specific ontologies or vocabularies, but we will describe our data with rich and subject specific keywords.

The data deposited in the repository will include references to other data and outputs of the project.

2.4 Increase data re-use

The instructions how to get access to the data as well as the provenance of the data and the information on methodology and analysis will be described in a readme file that will be connected to the record in the repository Zenodo.

The reuse of the supplemental data (questionnaires) and the analysis of the data (reports) will be provided under license CC BY 4.0.

We do not plan to archive data (using so-called *cold storage*) for long term preservation already during the project.

5 Other project outputs

All outputs that can be openly shared, such as reports (Report on networks analysis, Report on job shadowing and training of research managers, Report on Research management strategy implementation), strategies (Joint internalisation strategy for R&I, Human Recourses Strategy and recommendations (Policy recommendations for synergies among research and funding programmes) will be provided under license CC BY 4.0.

6 Allocation of resources

We will be archiving data (using so-called 'cold storage') for long term preservation after the project.

None of the used repositories (Zenodo) charge for their services.

For the management and proficiency of data including data processing, data policies, data guidelines, and data availability are responsible:

- At VSE, the person responsible for managing data in line with this DMP is: Aneta Kašílková;
- at KTU: the person responsible for managing data in line with this DMP is: Asta Savanevičienė;
- at EBS: the person responsible for managing data in line with this DMP is: Karmo Kroos;
- at UB, the person responsible for managing data in line with this DMP is Niccolò Cusumano.

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute.

7 Data security

Internally, **the data is to be stored in the private and protected shared MS Teams group, on Office 365 license of the coordinator.** This platform guarantees security, compliance and privacy and no person outside the team has access to it.

Project members can carry data with them on encrypted data carriers and password-protected laptops. All data centres where projected data are stored carry sufficient certifications. Encryption and dual authentication will be used to work with sensitive data. All project web services are addressed via secure HTTP (https://...). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

In case of collecting any data containing personal information ("sensitive data"), the responsible team member will store these data on the devices protected against unauthorized access and use the security strategy in coordination with his/her home institution. Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The risk of information loss, leak or vandalism in the project or organization is acceptably low.

In terms of open sharing, and as explained in Section 2.2 the data will be stored in trusted repository Zenodo, which is suitable for long term preservation and curation. Nevertheless, the datasets containing sensitive data cannot be stored in the repository.

8 Ethics

We will collect data connected to a person, i.e. "personal data". We explored General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) considerations and relevant materials. **We ask the data subjects for their consent. Each partner has its own consent form complying with the GDPR legal regulations of its country and the recommendations of its own institution. We will collect consent for our use of the data and for anonymization.** If possible, the data will be anonymized for reuse. In case anonymization would degrade the data to such an extent that it would not be suitable for reuse, or when privacy of the people involved would not be guaranteed, we will not proceed with the process of anonymization of the specific dataset.

The consent forms will be available for re-users. The purpose of processing the personal data is research of university practices (researchers, administrative support staff, research management staff, executive level; university bodies: deans' and rectors' collegiums, (inter)national advisory boards, academic senates), fulfilment of the project objectives, creation of project deliverables that require involvement of various stakeholders, especially internal employees of various levels. Their information is inherently collected by questionnaires or per notes from interviews and other specified data collection methods.

Specific deliverables need identification of involved persons due to the nature of the deliverable - as specified in the tables above:

- D1.1 – Project manual,
- D3.2 – Report on job shadowing and training of research managers and
- D4.3 – Report on submitted project proposals.

The data collection is not subject to ethical legislation.

9 Other issues

We use the [Data Stewardship Wizard](#) with its *Common DSW Knowledge Model* (ID: dsw:root:2.6.7) knowledge model to make our DMP. More specifically, we use the <https://dsw.vse.cz/wizard> DSW instance where the project has direct URL: <https://dsw.vse.cz/wizard/projects/f82f7571-a7f5-415c-87ca-f5a190b3a293>.

Common DSW Knowledge Model is designed in compliance with EU regulations and recommendations about research data management. Each WP will also adhere to local institutional and national recommendations and regulations like local research data policies or data protection policies.

Conclusion

The RIS4SEB project's Data Management Plan (DMP) establishes a clear and effective framework for the management, storage, and sharing of data generated or reused throughout the project. By aligning with the Horizon Europe guidelines and adopting FAIR principles, the plan ensures that data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, fostering transparency and enhancing the project's long-term impact.

To achieve these goals, the project utilizes the [Zenodo repository](#) for open-access data, ensuring secure, long-term preservation and compliance with metadata standards like the DataCite Metadata Schema.

Internally, data is managed within a private and protected shared MS Teams group, leveraging secure and reliable infrastructure to maintain confidentiality and prevent unauthorized access.

The DMP underscores the importance of ethical data management practices, particularly concerning personal data, which are handled in strict accordance with GDPR regulations and with a clear acknowledgment of the limitations of anonymizing data in cases involving small, uniquely identifiable groups.

The RIS4SEB consortium's commitment to accountability is demonstrated by the designation of specific data management personnel at each partner institution. These individuals ensure the consistent application of the DMP, promoting adherence to best practices and facilitating collaboration across all work packages.

In summary, the DMP for RIS4SEB exemplifies a thoughtful and comprehensive approach to data governance. By integrating ethical considerations, data management tools, and a decentralized but coordinated structure, the plan not only supports the project's objectives but also sets a high standard for data stewardship in collaborative research initiatives.

Finally, to reiterate, this DMP is to be read as a living document, with expected updates in months 15 and 36.

Annex 1

Recommendation for Data Organisation and Access to the Data generated in the project

RIS4SEB: Enhancing research and innovation synergies for schools of economics and business

This recommendation is based on the document [Data Organisation](#) by RDMkit and [Common DSW Knowledge Model](#) (ID: dsw:root:2.6.7) by Data Stewardship Wizard. It is dedicated to all members of the project RIS4SEB.

FILE NAMING

It is recommended to use an unified file naming system from the very beginning of the project. The file name should include these parts in this order:

- Date of creation – „YYYYMMDD“
- Project number / Experiment / Acronym – „RIS4SEB“
- Location / Coordinates – Institution of the partner: „VSE“, „EBS“, „KTU“
- Initials of the creator – Name of the creator: „JH“ etc.
- Type of data – „Questionnaire“, „Analysis“ etc.
- Version number: if appropriate – „V01“, „V02“, „V03“ etc.
- Reserve the last 3-letters for file format (e.g. .xls, .rtf, .mov, .tif, .doc)

Example: 20250201_RIS4SEB_VSE_JH_QUESTIONNAIRE_V01.csv

FILE FORMAT

During the active phase (collecting and interpreting data), it is possible to use proprietary device-specific file formats if needed. But for sharing the data with other members of the team and for long-term archiving, it is recommended to use open and non-proprietary formats of the data:

Type	Preferred	Acceptable
Rich Text Documents	ODT (.odt) Markdown (.md) LaTeX (.tex) for read-only documents: PDF/A (.pdf)	Office Open XML (.docx)
Plain Text Documents	Unicode text (.txt)	
Tabular Data	CSV (.csv, .tsv)	Office Open XML Workbook (.xlsx)
Containers and Compression	ZIP (.zip)	tar (.tar) gzip (.gz) bzip2 (.bz2)

FOLDER STRUCTURE

The structure of folders and subfolders should correspond to the project design. The folders should: a) have a self-explanatory name that is only as long as is necessary, and b) have a unique name – avoid assigning the same name to a folder and a subfolder.

METADATA AVAILABILITY

To prevent accidents with, e.g. renamed files, metadata information should always also be available elsewhere and not only through the file name. It is recommended to describe the metadata in the Readme file (see below).

If metadata need to change, embedding it in the file names may require renaming files during the project; and this may have implications for references to those files.

DATA ACCESS

A common space within MS Teams is set up for sharing information and documents between team members. Every team member has unlimited access to this team.

Project members can carry data with them on encrypted data carriers and password-protected laptops. All data centres where sensitive data are stored should carry sufficient certifications. To minimise the risk of sensitive data leakage, encryption and dual authentication should be used. The project web services should be addressed via secure HTTP (<https://...>).

README FILES

It is recommended to connect the readme file to datasets and other outputs of the project during the process of saving outputs to the Zenodo repository.

The readme file should contain:

- description of the data file (title, content, full metadata of the dataset/document, connected documents, PIDs, etc.),
- sharing options (for example, need of data sharing agreement),
- in case of closed dataset, contact for the person responsible for individual share and terms for sharing,
- license information.